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This deliverable reports on the pilot studies conducted to adjust the platform and the games within in order to properly address the cognitive and emotional needs of children with neurodevelopmental disabilities under the EMPOWER project.

Description

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INTRODUCTION

This deliverable contains a report of the main findings on the pilot studies conducted to adjust the platform and the games within to properly address the cognitive and emotional needs of children with neurodevelopmental disabilities under the EMPOWER project. It addresses the study designs, the findings, and the decisions taken to obtain the best setting and games for training children with neurodevelopmental disorders (NDD) within the EMPOWER project.

Whenever introducing a new proposal for assessment with the incorporation of new technologies, such as sensory, for neurodiverse children, there are many unknowns regarding the content of the instruments, whether they are suitable for the needs of children with NDD, whether they are accepted by children, whether they can be integrated in educational settings, whether the benefits surpass the costs, whether they are sufficiently informative, whether they have an adequate level, a challenge level of difficulty, whether the benefits transfer to other important functional domains etc. Pilot studies are defined as “*small-scale studies that test methods and procedures to assess the feasibility/ acceptability of an approach used within a large-scale study*”. (National Centre for Complementary and Integrative Health, 2017). Given the complexity of the Empower platform, as well as its applications, a series of 3 pilot studies were planned (see fig. 1 for the timeline of implementation). Additionally, we inserted a mini pilot in response to some adjustments made immediately after the second pilot study.

Figure 1. *Pilot studies planning and implementation*

The three pilot studies were planned to address each new development, as well as the effect of the implemented changes performed on the original designed tasks.

PILOT STUDY 1

A first pilot study was conducted in May- June 2023. We aimed to test the feasibility, usability, and the performance on 3 prototyped games (sustained attention, working memory, and inhibition games) of the EMPOWER digital platform. Also, we investigated the feasibility of integrating eye-tracking technology and wearables as complementary means to gather information along with the game-based assessment (see figure 2 for the diagram of the key components included in pilot1).

Method Study design

A mixed design study, using both quantitative and qualitative methods, such as observation and questionnaires, was conducted. We observed both verbal and non-verbal reactions as the children engaged in playing the games integrated on the platform. Data was collected from teachers and psychologists working with children with neurodevelopmental disorders, as well as from the children.

Figure 2. Key components used in pilot study 1. I.-Sustained attention game; II- Working memory; III- Inhibition;

Participants

Inclusion criteria for the participants were: participants to be diagnosed with NDDs with a level of cognitive ability to understand the instructions of the game, familiarized with technology, aged between 8-14.

Participants were 24 children with NDDs from Romania (n=12) and Portugal (n=12), aged between 8 and 13 years old. Of the final group of participants, 11 were with moderate intellectual disabilities (ID) and 1 with cognitive delay, 2 of which had associated autism spectrum disorders (ASD); 6 had also a diagnosis of hyperkinetic disorder, 1 with severe language delay. The sample from Portugal included 10 children with attention deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) and specific learning disorders (SLD), and 2 with SLD only.

The distribution of age is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Age distribution of participants in study 1

Age	Freq
8	3
9	4
10	4
11	1
12	10
13	2
Total	24

Procedure

The study was conducted both in Portugal and Romania and was approved by the Ethics Committee from both universities: Babeş-Bolyai University and University of Lisbon. Parents of children involved in the study signed informed consent. The procedure is illustrated in figure 3.

Each child was informed prior to the evaluation that they are going to play a series of 3 games on the tablet and that they will have to answer questions regarding the games they played. The duration of a session varied from 30 to 60 minutes. During the session the children played the 3 EMPOWER games and answered the questions regarding the game. During the evaluation in the room there were the child, the teacher or the therapist, and two researchers. Children were fitted with smart watch wearable; teachers filled in the participant information data and started the examination session. A short calibration was also conducted for the eye-tracker. Correct calibration of the Tobii eye-tracking system is critical to ensure that it is accurate and reliable throughout the process. The system realigns the gaze of the user around specific areas of the screen continuously during the process, thus enabling one to develop a tailored eye-tracking model. Proper calibration is necessary because it directly influences the accuracy of the obtained eye-tracking data.

Afterwards, children played each game starting with the first level and advancing to superior levels also based on achieving a certain level of performance.

As mentioned previously, the 3 games played by the children aim to evaluate and train working memory, sustained attention and inhibition. The additional information was collected before, during and after the games in relation to the variables addressed within the pilot.

Indirect measures were completed for each child by the teacher.

Figure 3. *Study procedure*

Measures

The Observation Checklist is a 17 items checklist to be completed by the teacher at the end of the session. The items describe the interaction between the child and the platform and games. The teacher must mark those statements that are true for the child. (e.g. "Follows the indications with attention."; "Is willing to play another game.")

Teacher usability questionnaire is completed by the teacher at the end of the session and the questions measure how suitable the games are for the child. It has a total of 12 items, 9 (1-8 and 10) of them are questions with "yes" or "no" answers, item 9 is a rating scale asking for an appreciation of the overall configuration (from 0 – very poor, to 3- excellent) and the last 2 items are questions with multiple choice answers which are covering suggestions for improvement and the most enjoyable part of the game for the child. (e.g. "Are the starting points easy enough for the children to get engaged in the game?"; "Is this game, the way it is designed, engaging for the child?").

Children usability questionnaire

Three questions ("Did you enjoy the game?"; "Was this game easy?"; "Do you need more help to play this game?") were addressed immediately after each of the game was played, and another 5 questions after all the games were completed (e.g. "Did you do well"; "Was this game interesting?"; "Was this game useful for you?").

The Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire (SDQ) (Goodman, 2001) is a short behavioral screening questionnaire. For this study we used the SDQ for children aged 4-17 years. The SDQ contains 25 items formulated in positive or negative attributes and are divided into 5 subscales (emotional problems, conduct problems, hyperactivity/inattention, problems with ageing and prosocial behavior). Reporting is done by the parent or teacher and is done on a scale from 0 to 2, where 0=not true, 1=more or less true, 2= definitely true (e.g. item: He worries a lot, often seems worried)

Childhood Executive Functioning Inventory (CHEXI) (Catale, Meulemans and Thorell, 2015) is an assessment tool for parents and teachers, that measures executive functioning in children aged 4 to 12 years. The questionnaire consists of 24 items. Item scores are summed into 4 subscales (working memory -WM, planning, regulation and inhibition), in addition by summing the scores for the first two subscales an index for WM is obtained, and for the next two an index for inhibition is obtained. Reporting is on a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 = definitely not true and 5 = definitely true. (e.g. item: Tends to do things without thinking beforehand about what might happen)

Measures with wearables. A smartwatch worn by participants on the non-dominant hand gathered physiological data (e.g. heart rate). After a thorough analysis of the on the shelf devices was conducted, we ended up using the Samsung Galaxy Watch 5 in our project. For monitoring heart activity, we used the readings from Samsung's Optical Heart Rate Sensor, which is designed to provide dependable heart rate measurements across diverse circumstances, making it compatible with our population, children with NDDs, as it does not require any specific pose or action from the user. Heart Rate Variability (HRV) is a quantitative measure that assesses variation in time intervals between successive heartbeats. Stress evaluation and response to stimuli have come to rely heavily on the computation and interpretation of HRV. It illustrates how the autonomic nervous system affects heart rate.

A score of Root mean squared successive differences between in between intervals (13 intervals) was computed.

Measures with the Eye Tracker device. A Tobii device was used to record and analyse eye movements, to make inferences about visual attention and general information processing. The ET device is placed in the holder that the manufacturer supplied, under screen position. The calibration is done using head/eye icons, the head is visualized and shows if the current position is correct or incorrect. The typical 5-point calibration is applied to the eye gaze position calibration. When the ET data recording is on, it gathers data while operating in the background. When the test is over, the raw data that was captured is saved in a MariaDB database. The platform game has access to real-time data and can start and stop capturing ET figures. Some of the measures

used in analysing eye movements include fixation duration and saccades. These metrics can reveal for how long and where the participant focuses their visual attention, how fast their gaze shifts, and the overall pattern of visual exploration. Based on raw data, additional heat maps were computed.

Results

Functionality

The three games tested in the first pilot ran according to the functional requirements. There were a few interruptions due to running issues in the attention game and in the working memory game, no interruptions were reported during the inhibition game.

The ET device position had to be reconsidered so that the hand of the child does not obstruct the access to the eyes of the participant of the ET device.

Also, some adjustments for the wrist watches were also inducted by the observation made during the first pilot study. A need to better position the smart wrist bracelet on the child forearm was identified.

Usability

Regarding usability we wanted to evaluate the overall configuration, the easiness of navigation in the menu and the clarity as far as indications and actions, given the characteristics of children belonging to different groups inside the NDD. For this we used the following instruments: Observation checklist, Student usability questionnaire (3 usability questions after each game; 5 usability questions at the end of the game session) and Teacher usability questionnaire.

The information collected from the **observation checklist** shows that 95,8% of children got out of the task during the breaks between the game tasks or until the answer screen was activated, 91,7% of them requested to be involved in the game one more time and understood the feedback provided by the game, 87,5% of children had enough time to observe the situation in the game, however 87,5% requested for a replay of the situation, 83,3% of them navigated with easiness inside the game, stayed involved in the game for 10 minutes or as long as the game lasted and offered the answers when they were supposed and not earlier. 79,2 of the children understood the indications without further explanation, 75% followed the indications with attention, 58,3% finalized the games, 45,8% pressed the answer key with a delay that affected the

overall performance, 20,8% of the children complained that the game is too long, 12,5% asked for a prolongation of time, but none of them was willing to play another game.

The answers gathered from the Teacher usability questionnaire show that 78,2% from the teachers think that the games have an appropriate level of difficulty for their students with NDDs, however 82,6% of them say that their students need help to understand the tasks, all of them agree that the starting points are easy enough for the children to engage with the game, 91,3% find the main menu intuitive, 95,4% find the estimated time to complete the tasks adequate, 78,2% say that the instructions are accessible to all their pupils, 90,9% consider that the game is easy to navigate, 30,4% consider that the game should be customizable, 50% find the game attractive for the children.

For the student usability questionnaire, we will present first the information collected after each game. Regarding the **attention game** 79,2% answered they had enjoyed the game a lot and 1 student did not enjoy the game at all, 41,7% said that the game was very easy and 45,8% - so/so, and 62,5%- answered they did not need help to complete that game.

Looking at the **working memory game**, 70, 8% of children enjoyed the game a lot and 29,2% so and so, 58,3% answered that the game was partially easy (so and so) and 41,7% said it was very easy, and 41,7% answered they needed more help in playing the game. Further, for the **inhibition game** 79,2% (out of 23) answered they enjoyed the game and 16,7% answered so and so, 83,3% claim that the game was very easy and 16,7% so and so, and 29,2% answered they needed more help.

Usability results based on the student questionnaire administered at the end of the game session show that all the children think that they did well on the game, 95,8% said that the game was interesting and also answered that they felt good about playing the game, 83,3% answered that the game was useful for them, 58,3% would like to play this game frequently, and 20,8% said that the game was difficult to play.

Performance

Performance on the games was also preliminary investigated to observe any faults on the actual task. For each of the designed tasks and measurements, we ran a descriptive analysis. On each of the tasks, we were able to see a range of performance, mean response times, means on levels, and how informative the different parameters are.

For sustained attention, differences in mean response times are small, and are not gradually increasing with the level.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics for Sustained attention

Level/statistics	CP	CA	EA	EP	MRT
L1_min	0	34	0	0	0
L1_max	18	42	8	17	0,89
L1_mean	13,63	41,13	0,83	3,58	0,68
L1_std.	5,8	1,77	1,78	5,11	0,18
L2_min	0	0	0	0	0
L2_max	18	42	19	18	0,92
L2_mean	13,39	36,52	1,83	3,04	0,56
L2_std.	5,94	12,4	4,62	4,29	0,24
L3_min	0	0	0	0	0
L3_max	18	42	40	16	1,41
L3_mean	14,61	35,43	4,74	2,61	0,67
L3_std.	5,4	12,52	9,91	4,39	0,24

CP- correct present; CA- correct absent; EA- error absent; EP- error present; MRT- mean response times

Table 3. Descriptive statistics for Working memory

Level/statistics	CPC	CS	CNS	LS
L1_min	0	0	0	0
L1_max	20	5	3	2
L1_mean	9	1,65	0,26	1,26
L1_std.	4,61	2,08	0,68	0,86
L2_min	0	0	0	0
L2_max	15	5	2	3
L2_mean	12,73	2,27	0,5	2,09
L2_std.	3,84	2,05	0,74	1,15
L3_min	7	0	0	1
L3_max	20	5	4	4
L3_mean	18,05	1,55	1	2,77
L3_std.	3,38	1,71	1,19	1,30

CPC-Correct peppers sorting, CS- correct selection and sorting; CNS- correct selected not sorted; LS- longest sequence.

Looking at the descriptive data from the Working memory game, we can observe that performance changes from one level to the other for most of the scores. Response times increase as expected. A reflexive approach is recommended, also to select the most adequate scores for this game.

Inhibition

Table 4. Descriptive statistics for the Inhibition game

Level/statistics	EP	CP	CA	MRT
L1_min	0	0	0	0
L1_max	6	6	6	10,19
L1_mean	0,83	5	4,35	4,28
L1_std.	1,58	2,04	2,38	2,57
L2_min	0	6	0	3,28
L2_max	6	6	6	10,48
L2_mean	0,65	?	5,35	4,48
L2_std.	1,74	0	1,74	1,68
L3_min	0	0	0	0
L3_max	6	6	6	5,03
L3_mean	0,7	5,7	5,04	3,81
L3_std.	1,73	1,25	2,05	0,94

CA- correct absent; CP- correct present; EP- error present; MRT- mean response time

In the inhibition task, mean response times were compared. In L3 the mean is smaller than on level 2. For Correct Present, there is no variation in performance.

Overall, for correct present there is small to no variation, and it is recommended to further analyse and improve level 2.

Construct Validity

A preliminary investigation on the construct validity was also addressed by correlating standardized measures of executive functions with the newly developed tasks. Strong correlations were obtained for the Romanian sample, on level 1 and level 3, for correct present (target hit) and attention difficulties. (level 1 $\rho(12) = -.686$; level 3 (11) $= -.763$).

Inhibition scores from our measure did not correlate with the inhibition index from CHEXI. However, CHEXI is an indirect measure of executive functions.

Scores on the Working memory measures did not correlate with the Working memory index from CHEXI, except for the longest sequence score on level 3.

Directions of action:

- New calibration app that is child- friendly.
- Fitting of the smart watch.
- Standardized setting with minimal requirements.
- Analysis of the difference in difficulty levels per games.
- Different academic performance measures.
- Reflect on game psychological variables and scores;
- Additional direct executive functions measures.
- Reflect on game psychological variables and scores;
- Additional direct executive functions measures.

PILOT STUDY 2

The present study

In this study we aimed to test the feasibility, usability, children performance and preliminary validity of the 5 games of the EMPOWER digital platform that propose to measure and train executive functions. For this pilot comparative to the first one we integrated feedback from teachers and students for the initial three games tested in the first pilot (sustained attention, working memory and inhibition), and added two more games (cognitive flexibility and delay of gratification). The calibration app for the eye-tracker used in two of the games is child- friendly. The smart watches were adjusted to better fit the size of the wrists of the small children. The game setting was reconsidered: the positioning of the eye- tracker, the illumination in the room etc.

Figure 4. Key components used in pilot 2.1.-I- Sustained attention game; II- Working memory; III- Inhibition; IV- Cognitive Flexibility; V- Delay of gratification

Method

Study design

As in the previous pilot, we conducted a mixed design study, using quantitative, as well as qualitative methods, through observation and questionnaires to investigate the functionality, and usability, and the performance of children with NDDs on the 5 executive function games of the EMPOWER digital platform. We observed both verbal and non-verbal reactions as the children were engaged in playing the games integrated on the platform. Data was collected from teachers and psychologists working with children with neurodevelopmental disorders, as well as from the children.

Participants

We kept the same inclusion criteria as in the first pilot study: participants to be diagnosed with NDDs, verbal, and with a level of cognitive ability to understand the instructions of the game, familiarized with technology, aged between 8-14.

The participants were 27 children, aged from 8 to 14 years old, from Romania (N=14) and Portugal (N=13). Most participants included in this study were 9 years old (25,93%) and 13 years old (25,93%), further the age distribution looks as follows: 14,81% were 8 years old, 11,11% were 11 years old and just as many 12 years old (11,11%), 7,41% were 10 years old, and 3,7% 14 years old. Looking at the gender distribution, most of them are males (66,67%). In the Romanian sample, 9 out of 14 have intellectual disability (ID), of which one with Down Syndrome, 3 have ASD with ID and ADD/HI (attention deficit disorder/hyperactivity and impulsivity), 4 AD. Most have at least 2 diagnostic labels within NDD. In the Portuguese sample 11 out of 14 have ADHD/ADD comorbid with SLD and 2 have SLD (specific learning disorder) without other comorbidities. For all children included in the study we have informed consent from the parent.

Procedure

Each child was informed prior to the evaluation that they are going to play a series of 5 games on the laptop/tablet and that they will have to answer questions regarding the games they played. The children were told that they can stop whenever they want and that is important to report sincere what they feel and think about the game. They were also informed about the confidentiality of their identity.

The duration of a session was about 60 minutes. During the session the children played the 5 games that train executive functions and answered the questions asked regarding the game. During the evaluation in the room were the child, the teacher or the therapist and the two researchers from the team. During the session the children have worn on their non-dominant hand a smartwatch that gathered physiological data (e.g. heart rate) and during attention game and delay of gratification game we also collected data using the eye tracker (ET).

The 5 games played by the children aim to evaluate and train working memory, cognitive flexibility, sustained attention, inhibition and delay of gratification. The additional information was collected before, during and after the games in relation to the variables addressed within the pilot. A second testing session was conducted to

collect performance data on direct cognitive/ emotion regulation standardized tasks. Indirect measures were completed for each child by the teacher.

Instruments

To test the usability, there were used the same measures as in the first pilot (Observation checklist, Usability questionnaire for teachers and Usability questionnaire for children).

We employed CHEXI as an indirect measure of executive functions and SDQ as a measure for emotional problems, conduct problems and prosocial behavior. For executive functions we also added the sustained attention subscale of the **Executive Skills Checklist (ESC)** (Diamond, 2016, Diamond, & Ling, 2016). ESC measures executive skills and is a scale provided by ADDitude. For this study we used the sustained attention subscale, which contains 7 items. The assessment is done by the teacher on a scale from 1 to 5, where 1=not a problem and 5=big problem. (e.g. "Rushes when working - careless/makes mistakes."). We also used the cognitive flexibility scale from ESC, that consists of 4 items.

The Security form aims to measure the physiological discomfort that the child might have felt during the session (5 items) (e.g. "Did you feel sick at any time during the game?").

Direct measures that assess working memory, sustained attention, inhibition, cognitive flexibility and delay of gratification were also added for this pilot and applied to the children in a separate session.

For the working memory (WM), inhibition and cognitive flexibility (CF) tasks we used REMEX – Assessing executive functions in children direct tasks (REMEX) (Costescu, David, Roșan, Cozma & Pădure, submitted).

The WM task assesses the child's ability to retain and manipulate information in real time. Materials and procedure: using 3 envelopes and paper geometric shapes the children have to complete the following 3 situations in the absence of the visual prompt, after the model envelope is presented to them: situation 1: 2 small crosses, one big heart; situation 2: a small triangle, a large circle and 2 large hearts; situation 3: small heart, large triangle, large cross and 2 small circles. Evaluation criteria: number of correctly

completed envelopes and number of errors per envelope (errors are: wrong geometric shape, geometric shape of incorrect size, extra geometric shape, missing geometric shape).

The inhibition task aims to assess the child's ability to reduce impulsive responses. Materials and procedure: the child will receive an answer sheet with a matrix on it and the assessor will read a story "Misha squirrel". The child is asked to block out a specific declarative knowledge and mark the opposite on the answer sheet. When they hear the word "up", they will make a mark on the bottom row of the matrix, when they hear "down", they will make a mark on the top row of the matrix and when they hear "middle", they will make a mark on the middle row of the matrix. Evaluation criteria: number of errors – marks made on the wrong row/row corresponding to another criterion, number of omissions (how many x's omitted) and the total number of errors (errors + omissions).

The CF task aims to assess the child's ability to adapt to change and think flexibly. Materials and procedure: the child will receive an answer sheet - a map with geometric figures and will have to mark certain geometric figures on each row, but the rule will change several times during the task, more specifically, every two rows (there is a total of 8 rows). The child must adapt to the changes in the instruction. Evaluation criteria: total number of errors (error = marking with the wrong symbol, missing a symbol, marking a geometric figure that was not mentioned in the instruction).

For the sustained attention we used an adapted form from the NEPSY attention task. Materials and procedure: the child will receive an answer sheet with multiple drawings on it and will have to circle two drawings or targets that are also on the top of the page (dog and face). The child has to look through the rest of the drawings on the sheet (distractors) and circle the targets in two different time intervals (180 sec/target). Evaluation criteria: total accuracy which represents the total number of targets (21 dogs and 8 faces) minus the errors (wrong drawing circled and omissions) and the total time to complete the task (seconds).

For delay of gratification, we have applied the experimental task “*marshmallow test*”. It measures a child's ability to delay rewards. Materials and procedure: we took children's favourite sweets, and they are given the option of waiting 15 minutes to eat two pieces of their favourite sweet or if they don't eat, they will only eat one piece. The child is left alone in the room and instructed that the experimenter will return shortly. The child was recorded to observe their behaviours and strategies used to resist. The prime evaluation criteria is the number of minutes and/or seconds that the child waited before eating the sweet. We also collected data regarding the strategies employed by the child to delay his/her gratification.

For academic performance measures we applied a reading fluency task, a reading comprehension task and a math computation task. For the reading tasks, passages were available in both languages with literary adaptation and adapted to the grade reading level. The passages for reading fluency task were: 1st- 2nd grade- “The Girl who hated books” (105 words), 3rd- 4th grade- “The Little Lead Soldier” (213 words) 5th- 6th grade “ The Anniversary of the Infanta” (303 words). Data as fluency score, time and errors were collected for this task. The texts provided for the reading comprehension task were for first level “The little girl who wanted to save the books”, adapted from Klaus Hagerup and Lisa Aisato, with 123 words and for second level “The Famous Five”, by Enid Blyton, with 295. For both levels 3 comprehension question were addressed. The math computation task consists 14 items: number comparison (symbolic), addition without regrouping, subtraction without regrouping, addition with regrouping, subtraction with regrouping, simple multiplication facts and division, multiplication with bigger numbers, division with bigger numbers, operations with fraction (same denominator, different denominator), operation with decimal numbers, operation with exponents and complex order of operations.

Results

Functionality

Four games ran according to the functional requirements, except for Attention game in which a smaller number of items within each session were recorded into the database, there were no game interruptions reported by teachers on the Teachers App (TA) for any of the 5 games. As for the functionality of the integrated technology for each game,

no unexpected events related to ET were reported by teachers on the TA except for 1 case during Delay of gratification. Still, we have to stress the fact that teachers need to be familiarized with TA in order to report events in a timely manner.

Usability

Regarding usability we wanted to evaluate the overall configuration, the easiness of navigation in the menu, clarity as far as indications, actions, engagement, satisfaction, instructiveness and customization. The instruments to address it are: The Observation Checklist; Student Usability Questionnaire and Teacher Usability Questionnaire. The answers gathered from the *observation checklist completed by the teachers* show that all children finalized the games and requested for a prolongation of time. Just one of the children didn't request to be involved in playing the game one more time and 92.6% of them followed the instructions with attention. 88.9% of the children stayed involved for as long as the game lasted and 85.2% of them navigated with easiness inside the game, understood the feedback provided and were willing to play another game. 81.5% answered when they were supposed to, 77.7% had enough time to observe the situations in the game and 70.4% of them understood the indications without further explanations. 11.1% of the children complained that the games are too long, complained that the games are boring or got off the tasks. Just 7.4% of them pressed the answer key with a delay that affected overall performance and for 7.4% of them showed increased frustration as they followed the game.

From the *usability questionnaire for teachers* the results show that there is easiness in navigation, the menu is intuitive, there is an adequate starting point for the games and the games are engaging. On the other hand, there were 33.3% of children for which the levels of difficulty were inadequate, 51,9% of them needed help to understand the tasks, 40.7% did not find the instructions accessible for students and 40.7% suggested that the games should be customizable. We also asked the teachers to rate the overall configuration of the game: 14,81% consider it very poor, 34, 01% rated it as poor, 7,41% answered it is as good, and 40,74% rated it as excellent. When asked what would they add to improve the game (possible options: colour, movement, rewards, more levels, more easy levels, support of different types, other), 74,07% chose rewards, 66,66% more difficulty levels, 48,14% colour, 40,74% movement, 18,51% support of different types, 11,11% easier difficulty levels, and 3,7% other (higher number of similar items at the same level).

To summarize, the games are appreciated for the easiness of navigation, intuitive menu, adequate starting points, and for being engaging for children with NDD. However, they need improvement on several aspects: adjusting level of difficulty for a third of the participants; understanding the task (more than 50%) (need to review instructions and task sequences), more accessible instructions for the students, and need for customization.

Results from *usability questionnaire for students* are presented below for each of the games.

For the attention game, 77,8% answered they had enjoyed the game a lot, 48,1% responded that the game was very easy, 11, 40,7%- responded that the level of difficulty was so/so and 2, 7,4% responded that the level was difficult. Most of the children completed the games without any help from their teachers.

For the working memory game, 15, 55, 6%, enjoyed the game a lot, 10, 37% so and so and 1, 3,7%, not so much. 37% answered that the game was very easy, 11, 40,7% so and so (easy) and 5, 18,5% found the game to be difficult. 11, 40,7% answered they needed more help in playing the game.

For the inhibition game, 81,5% answered they enjoyed the game a lot and 4, 14,8% so/so (enjoyment with the game). 19, 70,4% answered that the game was very easy to play, 6, 22,2% so and so, 1, 3,7%, considered the game was difficult to play. 11, 40,7% answered they needed more help in playing the game.

For the delay of gratification game, 77% answered they enjoyed the game a lot 23% said that enjoyed so and so the game. Regarding the difficulty of the game 38% children answered it was so and so and 62% said it was easy. None of the children considered that they needed more help. These results are reported only for the Portuguese sample (n=13). This results underline the need to address the level of challenge of the game.

For the cognitive flexibility game, 61.5% answered they enjoyed the game a lot 38.46% so/so (enjoyment with the game). 30.7% of them said the game was very easy and 69.23% mentioned that the game neither easy nor difficult. Approximately 8% of them said they need more help. These results are reported only for the Portuguese sample (n=13). This results underlines the need to address the level of challenge of the game.

Performance

We compared the results between the levels of the Attention games using the non-parametric test Wilcoxon. Results show there is little difference to none in between the three levels of sustained attention (no significant z scores were obtained). This draws the need to further perform modifications on the task.

Table 5. Within group comparisons of CP_means (Wilcoxon)

	Difference between level 2 and level1	Difference between level 3 and level1	Difference between level 3 and level2
Z	-1,265 ns	-,378 ns	,000 ns

CP- correct present;

A similar comparison was conducted for the mean response times on the Attention game.

Table 6. Within group comparisons of MRT

	Difference between level 2 and level1	Difference between level 3 and level2	Difference between level 3 and level1
Z	-1,689 ns	-1,778 ns	-2,803**

*MRT- mean response times; ns- non-significant; * *significant at $p < .01$*

A significant difference emerged between level 1 and level 3, but not between level 1 and level2, or level 3 and level 2.

Working memory game

Table 7. Within group comparisons of CPC_means (Wilcoxon)

	Difference between level 2 and level1	Difference between level 3 and level1	Difference between level 3 and level2
Z	-4,777 ^{b**}	-4,740 ^{b**}	-4,837 ^{b**}

*** - significant at $p < .01$; CPC- correct present classify*

There are significant differences between levels.

For the inhibition game

Table 8. Within group comparisons of correct responses means on the inhibition task (Wilcoxon) Test Statistics^o

	IH_L2_CP - IH_L1_CP	IH_L3_CP - IH_L2_CP	IH_L3_CP - IH_L1_CP	IH_L2_MRT - IH_L1_MRT	IH_L3_MRT - IH_L2_MRT	IH_L3_MRT - IH_L1_MRT
Z	-,378 ns	-1,000 ns	-,707 ns	-1,129 ns	-1,490 ns	-2,186 [*]

ns- non significant; * significant at $p < .05$;

There are significant differences between levels L1 and L3, on MRT.

For delay of gratification game

We compared differences for two scores, the waiting time (WT) and the success wait score per level (AW).

Within group comparisons of AW1 and AW2 per levels (Wilcoxon)

Table 9. Within group comparisons of AW3 per levels, WT1, WT2, & WT3

	DG_L2_AW3 - DG_L1_AW3	DG_L3_AW3 - DG_L1_AW3	DG_L3_AW3 - DG_L2_AW3	DG_L2_WT1 - DG_L1_WT1	DG_L3_WT1 - DG_L1_WT1	DG_L3_WT1 - DG_L2_WT1
Z	-1,414 ns	-,447 ns	-,577 ns	-,314 ns	-,674 ns	-,674 ns

ns- non-significant; L1, L2, L3- levels 1, 2, 3.

Table 10. Within group comparisons for waiting times between levels

	DG_L2_WT2 - DG_L1_WT2	DG_L3_WT2 - DG_L1_WT2	DG_L3_WT2 - DG_L2_WT2	DG_L2_WT3 - DG_L1_WT3	DG_L3_WT3 - DG_L1_WT3	DG_L3_WT3 - DG_L2_WT3
Z	,000 ns	-,447 ns	-,447 ns	-,405 ns	-,943 ns	-,365 ns

ns- non-significant

For the cognitive flexibility game, there were no notable differences between correct responses on levels 1, 2, and 3.

Convergent validity

We wanted to verify if the games we proposed correlate with other standardized measures that assess the same executive functions, and therefore to test for construct validity. The results are presented below.

There are no significant correlations between the sustained attention measures in the EMPOWER game and the ESC subscale score.

Table 11. Spearman correlations between scores on Sustained attention and ESC attention subscale score

	S A	AT_L1_ CP	AT_L1_M RT	AT_L2_ CP	AT_L2_M RT	AT_L3_ CP	AT_L3_M RT
Sustained attention	1	-,23	-,32	-,29	-,07	-,16	-,06

For the correlations with indirect measures of working memory, inhibition and cognitive flexibility we used the scores obtained on CHEXI.

For working memory, there are no significant correlation for the first level. For the second and third level we obtained significant correlation between the score for WM from CHEXI and correct sorting L2 ($r=-.566$, $p=.002$), L3 ($r=-.600$, $p=.001$), longest sorting sequence L2 ($r=-.674$, $p=.0$), L3 ($r=-.586$, $p=.001$) and mean response time L2 ($r=.599$, $p=.001$), L3 ($r=.560$, $p=.002$). The fact that the correlations are negative can be explained by the fact that CS and LS show good performance, meanwhile the CHEXI score shows deficits of WM.

For inhibition we found significant correlations with the inhibition score from CHEXI for the first level, more specifically for error present (EP) ($r=.523$, $p=.005$) and correct absent ($r=-.523$, $p=.005$); for the second level, Error present ($r=.459^*$), Error absent ($r=.472$), correct present ($r=-.472$), correct absent ($r=-.459$); from the third level, error present score and correct absent correlated with CHEXI inhibition.

Correlations with direct tasks

Attention

Table 12. Spearman correlation of the Empower sustained attention score with direct measures of attention

	DTA
L1_Correct_P	.876*
L1_Correct_A	.389
L2_Correct_P	.869**
L2_Correct_A	.742**
L3_Correct_P	.450
L3_Correct_A	.134

DTA- direct task attention; L1- level 1; L2- level 2; L3- level 3; P- correct present; A- correct absent.

Significant correlation with the direct task for sustained attention are only shown for the second level, correct present ($r=.869$) and correct absent ($r=.742$).

Working memory

Table 13. Spearman correlations between Empower working memory task and direct working memory task

	DTWM
L1_Longest_Seq	-.120
L2_Longest_Seq	-.453*
L3_Longest_Seq	-.450*

DTWM- direct task working memory; L1- level 1; L2- level 2; L3- level3; Longest_seq- longest sequence remembered.

Significant associations with the direct task for working memory emerged when correlating the longest sequence score with the direct task score for level 2 and level 3.

Inhibition

Table 14. Correlations between inhibition task and direct inhibition task

	DT IH
L1_Error_Absent	.437*
L1_Error_Present	.495*
L1_Corect_Present	-.437*
L1_Corect_Absent	-.495*
L2_Error_Absent	.815**
L2_Error_Present	.625**
L2_Corect_Present	-.815**
L2_Corect_Absent	-.625**
L3_Error_Absent	.632**
L3_Error_Present	.628**
L3_Corect_Present	-.632**
L3_Corect_Absent	-.628

L1, L2, L3- level 1, 2, 3; DT Inh- direct task inhibition.

We obtained significant correlations with the direct task for inhibition with all parameters of second level, error absent ($\rho=.815$), error present ($\rho=.625$), correct present ($\rho=-.815$) and correct absent ($\rho=-.625$) and third level, error absent ($\rho=.632$), error present ($\rho=.628$), correct present ($\rho=-.632$) and correct absent ($\rho=-.628$).

Cognitive flexibility

Table 15. Correlations between Empower cognitive flexibility scores and direct cognitive flexibility scores

	DT CF
L1_Correct_Response	-.391*
L1_Error Response	.503**
L2_Correct Response	-.330
L2_Error Response	.608**
L3_Correct Response	-.426*
L3_Error Response	.598**

L1, L2, L3- level 1, 2, 3

With the direct task for cognitive flexibility we obtained significant correlation for error response on all three levels: L1 ($\rho=.503$), L2 ($\rho=.608$) and L3 ($\rho=.598$), but also for correct response on level 1 and 3.

Delay of gratification

Table 16. Correlations between scores of Delay of gratification tasks and scores on direct delay of gratification task

	DT DG
L1_Wait_Time1	-.108
L1_Wait_Time2	.048
L1_Wait_Time3	-.015
L2_Wait_Time1	.045
L2_Wait_Time2	.056
L2_Wait_Time3	.134
L3_Wait_Time1	-.139
L3_Wait_Time2	-.097
L3_Wait_Time3	-.119

No significant correlations were obtained with the direct task for delay of gratification.

Method Study design

A mixed design study, using quantitative, as well as qualitative methods, through observation and questionnaires, was conducted to investigate the functionality, and usability, and also the performance of children with NDDs on 5 games of the EMPOWER digital platform. We observed both verbal and non-verbal reactions as the children were engaged in playing the games integrated on the platform. Data was collected from teachers and psychologists working with children with neurodevelopmental disorders, as well as from the children.

Modifications performed on the executive functions games: for Sustained attention- increase cognitive difficulty on the third level by introducing closer distractors to the target, and decreasing display times; inhibition- decrease time to respond; cognitive flexibility- improved instructions and increase of trials that require the child to hold the rule in the working memory; delay of gratification- increase in the proposed waiting time and introduction of a reward consisting of playing for a certain amount of time at child's choice.

Participants

The participants were 6 children (N=6), aged from 5 to 10 years old, all of them were males with diagnosis of ASD, from a therapy center in Constanța, Romania.

Procedure

Each child was informed prior to the evaluation that they are going to play a series of 5 games on the laptop/tablet and that they will have to answer questions regarding the games they played. The children were told that they can stop whenever they want and that is important to report sincere what they feel and think about the game. They were also informed about the confidentiality of their identity.

The duration of a session was about 60 minutes. During the session the children played the 5 games that train executive functions and answered the questions asked

regarding the game. During the evaluation in the room were the child, the teacher or the therapist and the two researchers from the team. During the session the children have worn on their non-dominant hand a smartwatch that gathered physiological data (e.g. heart rate) and during attention game and delay of gratification game we also collected data using the eye tracker (ET).

The 5 games played by the children aim to evaluate and train working memory, cognitive flexibility, sustained attention, inhibition and delay of gratification. The additional information was collected before, during and after the games in relation to the variables addressed within the pilot. A second testing session was conducted to collect performance data on direct cognitive/ emotion regulation standardized tasks. Indirect measures were completed for each child by the teacher.

Instruments

For the third mini pilot we used the same measurements as in the other two pilot to test the usability from the teacher perspective. From children perspective, usability was tested with System Usability Scale for User Testing with Children (Putnam et. al., 2020) and other four questions that are addressed before and after each game.

System Usability Scale for User Testing with Children (Putnam et. al., 2020) was given to the child right after completing playing all the games to see how useful, easy and pleasant the games were. The questionnaire has 14 items and are answered on a 5 points likert scale, where 1 is not at all and 5 is a lot. (e.g. "I always felt like I knew what to do next while playing the games."; "Some of the things I had to do while playing didn't make sense."; "I really enjoyed playing these games.") In addition to this scale, children had to answer 4 questions before and after each game. The aim of this question is to measure if they like the game (e.g. "Do you think you will like this game?"), their self-efficacy ("Do you think you will do well even if some parts are more difficult than others?") regarding the game, their motivation to play the game ("Do you feel motivated to play this game?") and their expectation respectively how they perceived the difficulty of the game ("Do you expect the game to be easy?").

The Security form aims to measure the physiological discomfort that the child might have felt during the session (5 items) (e.g., “Did you feel sick at any time during the game?”).

For the third pilot we also changed the direct measurements of the academic performance with the Academic Performance Rating Scale (APRS) (DuPaul, Rapport & Perriello, 1991). The APRS is a 19 items scale that reflects the teacher perception of children’s academic performance and abilities in classroom settings. It includes items directed towards work performance in various subject areas (e.g., “Estimate the percentage of written math work completed relative to classmates”), academic success (e.g., “What is the quality of this child’s reading skills?”), behavioral control in academic situations (e.g., “How often does the child begin written work prior to understanding the directions?”), and attention to assignments (e.g., “How often is the child able to pay attention without you prompting him/her?”). The instrument has a likert scale format from 1 (never or poor) to 5 (very often or excellent).

Direct measures that assess working memory, sustained attention, inhibition, cognitive flexibility and delay of gratification were applied to the children in a separate session, and were the same tasks applied in the second pilot, the only change we made was in the delay of gratification task. We have applied an experimental task adapted from Kochanska et al. (1996). Materials and procedure: an opaque bag with different types of candies and other sweets, a timer. The child is informed about the bag with sweets, and that they can choose the candy they want. If they don’t touch the bag or the sweets, they will have 2. If they touch anything they can only have 1. They must choose the sweet they want by verbally telling the assessor (without using their hands). The assessor will fiddle with the bag, dropping items on the floor, etc., unable to get the sweet the child wants. This task will take a maximum of 5 min. The child is not informed about the maximum duration of the task. If the child touches any sweet or the bag the time stops and the task ends.

Results

Functionality

In terms of functionality, we wanted to see if the games are running according to the functional requirements. There were no reports of dysfunctionalities regarding the games, but 2 out of 6 children were able to exit the game by pressing the exit icon on the screen and reconnect to another preset user. With this in mind, we will come up with solutions to fix this problem (e.g. blocking unnecessary functions while the student is using the tablet/laptop) so that the results obtained by each child will be recorded accurately on the teacher's application. There were no eye tracker events reported on the teachers application.

Usability

Regarding usability we wanted to evaluate the overall configuration, the easiness of navigation in the menu, clarity as far as indications, actions, engagement, satisfaction, instructiveness and customization. The instruments to address it are: The Observation Checklist; Student Usability Questionnaire and Teacher Usability Questionnaire.

The answers gathered from teachers through the *Observation Checklist* show that 2 out of 6 children navigated with easiness inside the game, 3 of them understood the indications without further explanations, 2 of the children answered at the right time and not earlier, the performance of 4 out of 6 children was affected by pressing the key with a delay, 2 of them stayed involved in the game for 10 minutes/as long as the game lasted, 2 children complained that the game is too long and 2 that the game is boring. 2 out of 6 followed the indications with attention, and 5 of them finished the games, 4 of them get out of task in the breaks between the games. None of the children requested for a prolongation of time, 4 of the children willingly played another game. 3 out of the 6 children understood the feedback provided and the frustration of 1 child increased while playing the game.

From the data gathered with the *usability questionnaire for teachers* we found out that none of the teachers considered that the level of difficulty was appropriate for their students, the instructions were not accessible for their pupils and that the children needed help in understanding the tasks. Also, unanimously answered that the games need to be customisable. 4 of them agree that the starting point is easy enough for

children to engage with the game. Just one of them considers that the estimated time to complete the tasks is adequate. 5 out of 6 answered that the game is easy to navigate. All of them ranked the overall configuration of the game as good (very poor, poor, good, excelent). 3 of them would add more levels to the games, all of them would add easier levels, 3 would add different types of support and 2 would add rewards.

Regarding the usability results from the students, we encountered several problems in collecting the data, two of the participants are nonverbal, 1 has selective mutism and didn't talk during the session, the rest of the children presented difficulty in understanding the question and have fixated on certain answers.

Differences between the levels of the games based on performance

For Sustained attention

Table 17. Differences between levels on sustained attention

	Difference between level 2 and level1 on error absent	Difference between level 2 and level1 on Error present	Difference between level 2 and level1 on correct present	Difference between level 2 and level1 on correct absent
Z	-0.921 ns.	-1.069 ns.	-1.069 ns.	-0.921 ns.

Based on the data, no notable difference is present when comparing Attention parameters on levels.

Inhibition

Differences between level 1 and level 3, as well as between level 1 and level 2, were found for correct present (between level 2 and level 1, $z = -2.23^*$; between level 3 and level 1, $z = -2.214^*$), correct absent (between level 3 and level 1, $z = -2.21^*$; between level 3 and level 1, $z = -2.04^*$), and mean response times. However, no notable difference, based on this data, was obtained between level 2 and level 3.

Cognitive flexibility

We found differences between L1 and L2: Cr_L1_L2: $z = -1,997$, $p < .05$, but not between level 2 and level 3.

Delay of gratification

In the case of the delay of gratification, significant differences emerged between level 1 and level 2 waiting trial ($z = -2.201^*$). No other differences were apparent based on the current data.

When looking at these results, we take into consideration the small sample ($n=6$) of this study. Beside the size of the sample, it's important to bring upfront the impairments of the children involved in the study, which are on the more severe spectrum of NDDs.

Participant 1, male, 7 years old, with ASD is nonverbal and at the beginning of the session was highly agitated and didn't want to cooperate, until he entered in contact with the tablet. We started the session, but he was dependent on the educator's physical prompt (hand on hand), also searched a lot for feedback from her during the session. While the session progressed, he was able to play the game without physical prompt and just with simple instructions provided by the therapist. During the session he seemed agitated, fidgeted, kept changing position in the chair, put his hand in the mouth and had to be reminded to pay attention at the tasks.

Participant 2, male, 5 years old, with ASD, verbal (mostly repeating the words he hears) presented with cold (running nose). Easily distracted during the games, short attention span, did not concentrate on the tasks, pressed the keys randomly or he kept touching the same element on the tablet in a fixated way (e.g. the crates in the cognitive flexibility game) until redirected.

Participant 3, male, 7 years old, ASD, verbal (stereotyped idiosyncratic usage of words). During the session there was a lot of fidgeting, either playing with the hands (clapping, randomly pressing on the screen) either the chair pooling or putting his face

very close to the screen of the tablet. He showed difficulty to concentrate on the tasks, but also showed good performance while concentrating.

Participant 4, male, 5 years old, ASD, verbal. During the session showed good attention, kept his position in the chair and concentrated well on tasks, but he showed signs of physical distress from the smart watch, and during and after the delay of gratification game we observed a decrease in the enthusiasm and willingness to play, he took a break and then came back to finish the DG game. For the last game, WM, the child didn't want to continue playing after finishing the first level and we stopped the session.

Participant 5, male, 10 years old, ASD, verbal according to his therapist (didn't speak during the session). Showed good attention, and a very good understanding of tasks, at the end of the sessions he showed signs of fatigue and frustration (facial expressions and aggressively pressed on the screen).

Participant 6, male 5 years old, ASD, verbal. During the session we noticed delays in response, lack of concentration and general apathy, all this affected his performance on the games.

We verified the construct validity of the platform through convergent validity, so we can examine whether the newly developed tasks correlate well with other measures that are theoretically related to the same construct. Therefore, we used direct tasks derived from standardized tasks (i.e. visual search task, marshmallow task) or developed and validated previously by the first author (REMEX Battery).

Correlations with direct task for sustained attention show that CP (correct present) on L1 (level 1) and L3 (level 3) correlate with attention accuracy, $p < .05$ (.812*; .893*). All CP correlate strongly with Attention_sec (-1**, -.943**, -.880*). No other parameter correlates with direct measures of attention.

Correlation with the Inhibition task show high correlation at L1 with MRTP (-.928**), at level 2 with CA (.823*) and at level 3 with EA (-.895*).

For cognitive flexibility (CF), L1, ER (number of errors) correlates strongly with CR (correct response) (-.841) and NPE (non pervasive errors) scores (-.841), L2, ER (-.812*), CCS (total category correct sort) (.868*) and L3, ER (-.899*), CCS (.893*), NPE (-.841*).

The correlations for delay of gratification (DG) show that L1_WT1 (waiting time at

level 1) - correlates with DG-Eat (-.828*) and L2_WT2 (waiting time level 2) - correlates with DG_time_min (.880*).

We also examined whether the scores on the game correlate with the academic performance measured through APRS. The results of the analyses show that Attention-L1_CP correlates with academic productivity (.802*), Working memory correlates with academic success: L1_CS (correct sorting) (.853*), L1_LS (longest sorting sequence) (.853*), impulse control (L1_CS, .867*; L1_LS, .867*; L2_CNS – correct not sorting, -.853*) and academic productivity: L1_CS (.853*), L1_LS (.853*), L2_CNS (-.871). Inhibition too correlates with academic success: L2_CA (correct absent) (.826*), impulse control: L2_CA (.876*) and academic productivity: L2_MRTP (mean response time present) (.820*), L2_CA (.898*). There were no correlations with CF and DG.

Directions of action:

- Further examination for the attention game.
- Further examination of the data for game levels by using Item response theory,
- Keep the Academic performance rating scale for the validation study
- Training for teachers to discuss who benefits the most for playing the games

PILOT STUDY 3- INCOMING (NOVEMBER 2024)

This final pilot will address the effects on usability, feasibility, functionality, and performance of the emotion games that were recently developed, but also to investigate the effects drawn by the last modifications performed on the 5 executive functions games on the previously mentioned attributes.

Research design

The research design for this study is similar to those from the previous studies. As in the previous pilot, we will employ a mixed design study, using quantitative, as well as qualitative methods, through observation and questionnaires to investigate the functionality, and usability, and also the performance of children with NDDs on all the games of the EMPOWER digital platform. We will observe both verbal and non-verbal reactions as the children play the games integrated on the platform. Data will be collected from teachers and psychologists working with children with neurodevelopmental disorders, as well as from the children.

Participants

Inclusion criteria are: participants to be diagnosed with NDDs, verbal, and with a level of cognitive ability to understand the instructions of the game (based on teachers assessment), able to use touch-screen technology, aged between 8-14. We will include 20-24 participants from Romania and Portugal who did not play the games previously.

Procedure

Each child will be informed prior to the evaluation that they are going to play a series of games on the laptop/tablet and that they will have to answer questions regarding the games they played. The children will be informed that they can stop whenever they want and that it will be important to report sincerely what they feel and think about the game. They will be also informed about the confidentiality of their identity.

Two sessions will be held, as they are to play each all the games. Each session is estimated to last for about 60 minutes, including breaks.

During the first session the children will play the 5 games that train executive

functions and will answer the usability questions. During the evaluation in the room there will be the child, the teacher or the therapist and the two researchers from the team. During the session the children will wear on their non-dominant hand a smartwatch to gather physiological data (e.g. heart rate) and during attention game and delay of gratification game we will collect data using the eye tracker (ET).

The 5 games played by the children aim to evaluate and train working memory, cognitive flexibility, sustained attention, inhibition and delay of gratification. Other 3 games address emotion recognition and naming, emotion intensity, emotion understanding, and emotion regulation. All these abilities are integrated in three games around a farmer's fair theme. Also, each game has three levels of difficulty.

Additional information will be collected before, during and after the games in relation to the variables addressed within the pilot (see below the instruments on usability). A second testing session will be conducted to collect performance on the emotion games, as well as data on direct cognitive/ emotion regulation standardized tasks. Indirect measures will be completed for each child by the teacher (e.g. CHEXI, SDQ, ESC (described previously)).

Instruments:

From children perspective, usability was tested with System Usability Scale for User Testing with Children (Putnam et. al., 2020) and other four questions that are addressed before and after each game.

System Usability Scale for User Testing with Children (Putnam et. al., 2020) was given to the child right after playing all the games to see how useful, easy and pleasant the games were. The questionnaire has 14 items and are answered on a 5 points Likert scale, where 1 is not at all and 5 is a lot. (e.g. "I always felt like I knew what to do next while playing the games."; "Some of the things I had to do while playing didn't make sense."; "I really enjoyed playing these games."). In addition to this scale, children had to answer 4 questions before and after each game. The aim of these questions is to measure if they liked the game (e.g. "Do you think you will like this game?"), their self-efficacy regarding the game ("Do you think you will do well even if some parts are more difficult than others?"), their motivation to play the game ("Do you feel motivated to play this game?"), and their expectations on difficulty of the game and the perceived difficulty of the game ("Do you expect the game to be easy?").

The Security form aims to measure the physiological discomfort that the child might have felt during the session (5 items) (e.g. “Did you feel sick at any time during the game?”).

Academic emotion regulation questionnaire (AERQ) (Buric et al., 2016) measures emotion regulation strategies they employ in academic settings through eight scales each addressing one strategy: avoiding situations, developing competences, redirecting attention, reappraisal, suppression, respiration, venting, and seeking social support. The questionnaire has 39 items.

For the third pilot we also changed the direct measurements of the academic performance with the Academic Performance Rating Scale (APRS) (DuPaul, Rapport & Perriello, 1991). The APRS is a 19 items scale that reflects the teacher perception of children’s academic performance and abilities in classroom settings. It includes items directed towards work performance in various subject areas (e.g., “Estimate the percentage of written math work completed relative to classmates”), academic success (e.g., “What is the quality of this child’s reading skills?”), behavioural control in academic situations (e.g., “How often does the child begin written work prior to understanding the directions?”), and attention to assignments (e.g., “How often is the child able to pay attention without you prompting him/her?”). The instrument has a Likert scale format from 1 (never or poor) to 5 (very often or excellent).

Direct measures that assess working memory, sustained attention, inhibition, cognitive flexibility and delay of gratification will be applied to the children in a separate session, and these are the same tasks applied in the second pilot, except for the delay of gratification task.

An experimental task was adapted from Kochanska et al. (1996). Materials and procedure: an opaque bag with different types of candies and other sweets, a timer. The child is informed about the bag with sweets, and that they can choose the candy they want. If they don’t touch the bag or the sweets, they will have 2. If they touch anything they can only have 1. They must choose the sweet they want by verbally telling the assessor (without using their hands). The assessor will fiddle with the bag, dropping

items on the floor, etc., unable to get the sweet the child wants. This task will take a maximum of 5 min. The child is not informed about the maximum duration of the task. If the child touches any sweet or the bag the time stops and the task ends.

SUMMARY OF RESULTS

Overall, by conducting a series of three pilot studies with children with NDD such as intellectual disabilities, autism spectrum disorders, ADHD, specific learning disorders, communication disorders, we will be able to adjust games and integrated technology to a shape that is acceptable to address executive functions and emotion regulation. These studies were helpful not only in further developing the games for configuration, construct and difficulty, but also in identifying relevant scores to consider, to observe various hinders we may encounter for the validation and RCT studies, such as setting requirements for the integrated technologies, types of relevant scores not only in games, but also derived scores from the parameters of wearables and Eye-tracking.

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